

NS3 simulation of OLSR protocol for flying Ad hoc Network

· Rohit Chaudhary

· Neha Gautam

· Vishnu Kumar

· Naman

Abstract

This research paper presents a comprehensive analysis of the performance metrics, including throughput, latency, packet delivery ratio, and node speed, in a flying ad hoc network (FANET). Flying Ad-hoc Networks (FANETs) represent an autonomous technology utilizing Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) to establish dynamic wireless networks. Traditional routing protocols for mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) or vehicular ad hoc networks (VANETs) often fall short in addressing the unique challenges posed by FANETs, such as high mobility and frequent topological changes. In this paper we investigate the impact of varying packet sizes on these metrics under the Optimized Link State Routing (OLSR) protocol in three-dimensional (3D) scenarios. By leveraging residual energy and node degree alongside 3D-position information, the protocol enhances packet delivery ratio, average throughput, and minimizes routing overhead and end-to-end delay. Simulated using the NS-3 simulator, the proposed protocol demonstrates significant performance improvements over benchmark protocols. Additionally, this paper contributes to the understanding of FANETs by offering a comprehensive survey covering architecture, mobility models, routing techniques, and simulation tools, along with a critical analysis of existing routing protocols and future challenges in the field.

Keywords: Optimized Link State Routing, proactive protocol, flying ad hoc network (FANET), MPR (Multi point relay), UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles), mobility

1. Introduction

Recent advancements in electronic, sensor, and communication technologies have led to the development of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) systems capable of autonomous flight or remote operation without human personnel aboard. These UAVs, commonly referred to as drones, offer versatility, flexibility, easy deployment, and relatively low operating costs.

A UAV [Fig:1], essentially a miniature pilotless aircraft, can navigate the skies and be controlled remotely. One significant application of UAV technology is in Flying Ad-Hoc Networks (FANETs), where drones are deployed to facilitate information exchange in scenarios where traditional networks are impractical, such as in areas obstructed by mountains, bodies of water, or during natural disasters like hurricanes or flash floods.

FANET UAVs are equipped with sensors, a Global Positioning System (GPS), and smart digital cameras, enhancing their efficiency in navigating and operating within high-risk environments. These capabilities enable FANETs to gather and transmit critical data, aiding in disaster response, surveillance, and various other applications.

Fig: 1

1.1 Objectives

The primary objective of this research is to conduct a systematic investigation into the performance of FANETs utilizing the Optimized Link State Routing (OLSR) protocol in a three-dimensional space. Specifically, our objectives are as follows:

To analyze the impact of varying packet sizes on the throughput of the FANET.

To measure the latency experienced by data packets as a function of packet size.

To evaluate the packet delivery ratio under different network conditions and packet sizes.

To assess the influence of node speed on the overall performance of the FANET.

By achieving these objectives, we aim to provide insights into the behavior of FANETs and contribute to the body of knowledge surrounding aerial ad hoc networking.

1.2 Motivation

OLSR is a proactive routing mechanism that relies on the link state information. The Key feature of OLSR is the MPR. The topology control messages are only forwarded through MPR nodes, which effectively restrain the overhead of broadcasting. The transmission of hello messages and topology control (TC) messages are crucial procedures in OLSR to detect the network topology and estimate the link state as shown in flowchart [Fig: 2]. Each node broadcasts the hello message to all its neighbors periodically, and the message contains the sender node's information and its neighbors information. Through the exchange of hello messages, each node detects its 1-hop neighbors and 2-hops neighbors. In

OLSR, only the MPR nodes are allowed to forward the TC message to the whole network. The TC message contains the information about the selectors of each MPR node. The selectors refer to the nodes that select the nodes as their MPR nodes. This information on selectors is embedded in its neighbor's hello message, and the messages are then written into the TC messages. In addition, the nodes detect the topology of the whole network through the received TC message. Once a TC message arrives, the node can update its routing table and calculate the shortest path to the destinations by the Dijkstra algorithm. However, the traditional broadcast mechanism for hello messages and TC messages in OLSR is not suitable in FANET since the speed of UAVs can exceed 100 mph and the topology of the network may change dramatically. The information in the received hello message and TC message may be outdated. For a TC message, its default interval is 5 seconds in the classic OLSR design, which faces a serious problem of being out-dated in a sparsely distributed network and becomes almost useless for estimating the topology and calculating the routing paths. In this case, the end-to-end delay and packet delivery ratio of the collaborate operation in sparse FANETs are unacceptable. Moreover, the routing strategy of OLSR, which employs Dijkstra, is not suitable in FANET for the various durations of the link existent time, which leads to further deteriorated performance in a sparse FANET. Fortunately, the trajectory of UAVs can be pre-planned. Although the planned trajectory may be adjusted during the duration of cooperation among UAVs, the short-term planned trajectories are considered to be certain within a few seconds. Thus, it is possible to improve the accuracy of the topology estimation by sharing the short-term trajectories through hello messages and TC messages. Importantly, reasonable modeling of the trajectories can effectively compress the additional overhead of packets. Hence, we proposed trajectory-OLSR, which aims to improve the end-to-end delay and packet delivery ratio in sparse FANETs. In T-OLSR, the short-term trajectories of each node within several seconds are modeled using a three-order polynomial. Then, the coefficients of these polynomials are embedded as an additional section into the hello message and TC message. In other words, the short-term trajectory of a UAV is shared as several coefficients of three-order polynomials, which slightly increase the extra overhead of the packets. Based on these short-term coefficients of the trajectories, the nodes can accurately estimate the position of other nodes and reconstruct the real-time topology of the network once they receive the hello packets or TC packets. To utilize the trajectory information in the route-finding process, Q-learning is used as the route-finding mechanism to further refine the network's performance, while a specifically-designed packet forwarding sequence that considers progressive image transmission is also adopted to improve the image quality. This proposed mechanism can efficiently enhance the performance of traditional OLSR in sparse FANETs in terms of the end-to-end delay and packet delivery ratio.

Fig: 2

2. System Architecture and Simulation Setup

2.1 Network Topology

For the purpose of this research, a basic Flying Ad Hoc Network (FANET) simulation is employed to evaluate the performance of the network under various conditions. The network topology comprises 15 Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) distributed randomly within a three-dimensional space. These UAVs serve as mobile nodes in the network, engaging in wireless communication with each other to facilitate data exchange and coordination.

To simulate realistic movement patterns of the UAVs within the network, a Gauss-Markov mobility model is utilized. The Gauss-Markov model is a stochastic mobility model that incorporates both random and deterministic components to simulate the movement trajectories of UAVs over time. In this model, the mobility of each UAV is influenced by a combination of its current position, velocity, and environmental factors, resulting in dynamic and non-linear movement patterns.

The Gauss-Markov mobility model allows for the emulation of various mobility behaviors observed in real-world scenarios, including random movements, periodic patterns, and directional changes. By capturing the inherent randomness and predictability of UAV movements, this model provides a more realistic representation of the spatial distribution and movement behaviors of UAVs within the FANET.

The utilization of the Gauss-Markov mobility model in the simulation framework enables the study of how the movement dynamics of UAVs affect the network topology, connectivity, and overall performance of the FANET. By incorporating realistic mobility patterns, the simulation results can offer valuable insights into the behavior of FANETs in dynamic and unpredictable environments.

2.2 NS-3 Simulation Environment

The ns-3 network simulator is chosen as the simulation tool for its extensive capabilities in modeling and simulating complex network scenarios with high fidelity. ns-3 provides a flexible and modular framework that allows researchers to design and implement custom network protocols, algorithms, and simulation scenarios tailored to their specific requirements.

One of the key strengths of ns-3 is its support for wireless communication simulations, making it particularly suitable for studying ad hoc and mobile networks like FANETs. It offers a comprehensive suite of built-in models and modules for simulating various aspects of wireless communication, including propagation models, channel characteristics, and interference effects. This enables researchers to accurately model the wireless environment and analyze the performance of communication protocols in realistic conditions.

Moreover, ns-3's modular architecture facilitates the integration of custom scripts and configurations to create complex simulation scenarios. Researchers can develop scripts to define the network topology, configure node behaviors, generate traffic patterns, and implement routing protocols like OLSR. This level of customization allows for fine-grained control over the simulation parameters and enables the exploration of a wide range of network configurations and scenarios.

In the simulation environment, custom scripts are utilized to initialize UAV nodes, simulate their movement using the Gauss-Markov mobility model, and orchestrate their communication activities. These scripts control the generation of traffic flows between nodes, the establishment of routes using the OLSR routing protocol, and the collection of performance metrics such as throughput, latency, and packet delivery ratio.

Overall, ns-3 provides researchers with a powerful platform for conducting in-depth studies of FANETs and evaluating the performance of network protocols under varying conditions. Its flexibility, modularity, and extensive feature set make it a valuable tool for advancing research in the field of aerial ad hoc networking.

2.3 OLSR Implementation

OLSR is a proactive routing protocol which is designed especially for adhoc networks. OLSR is a proactive routing protocol. In proactive protocol every node maintains one or more tables representing the entire topology of the network. Because of the proactive nature, this protocol has a

benefit of having routes quickly available whenever required. To maintain the up-to-date routing information, all the nodes declared and broadcast their topology information in the whole network OLSR provides following features:

- It reduces the size of control packets by declaring a node as a multi-point-relay (MPR) selector to each and every node of its neighbor.
- By using those MPRs which were selected, it reduces to scattering its messages to the whole network. OLSR uses MPR through which it is able to reduce the whole network traffic and also reduces the flooding in the network which arises when every node transmits data to each other to send the message to the exact destination. Hence, this routing protocol is best fit for large and dense ad hoc networks.

2.3.1 Proactive vs. Reactive Protocols

In the realm of ad hoc routing protocols, two main categories exist: proactive and reactive. Proactive protocols, such as OLSR, maintain up-to-date routing information by periodically exchanging control messages among neighboring nodes. This approach ensures that routing tables are always available, enabling faster packet forwarding at the expense of increased overhead. In contrast, reactive protocols establish routes only when needed, resulting in lower overhead but potentially longer route setup times.

2.3.2 Standard OLSR Implementation

The standard OLSR implementation within the ns-3 simulation environment follows the proactive approach to routing. It utilizes a distributed algorithm to maintain routing tables and establish shortest paths between nodes in the FANET. OLSR achieves this by periodically exchanging link state information, known as Hello and Topology Control (TC) messages, among neighboring nodes. These messages allow each node to construct and maintain a topology map of the network, which is used to calculate and update routing tables.

2.3.3 Modified OLSR Protocols

While the standard OLSR implementation is suitable for many ad hoc networking scenarios, modifications may be necessary to accommodate the specific requirements of FANETs. Researchers have explored various extensions and enhancements to the OLSR protocol to improve its performance in aerial environments. These modifications may include adjustments to parameters such as message transmission intervals, neighbor sensing mechanisms, and routing table update strategies.

2.3.4 Customizations for FANETs

In the context of this research, minimal modifications are made to the standard OLSR implementation within ns-3 to adapt it for FANET simulations. These customizations may involve fine-tuning protocol parameters to account for factors such as node mobility, communication range, and network dynamics unique to aerial environments. By tailoring the OLSR protocol to the specific characteristics of FANETs, researchers can more accurately assess its performance and effectiveness in real-world scenarios.

Overall, the implementation of the OLSR protocol within the ns-3 simulation environment provides researchers with a powerful tool for studying routing and communication in FANETs. By leveraging the proactive nature of OLSR and customizing it for aerial environments, researchers can gain valuable insights into the behavior and performance of ad hoc networks operating in three-dimensional space.

2.4 Parameter Settings

Several parameters are configured and controlled within the ns-3 simulation environment to study the performance of the FANET under different scenarios. These parameters include:

Packet size: Varied to evaluate its impact on network throughput and latency.

Transmission range: Determines the communication range between UAV nodes.

Mobility parameters: Govern the movement characteristics of UAVs, such as speed and direction.

Simulation duration: Defines the duration of the simulation run to observe network behavior over time.

The values of these parameters are chosen based on the research objectives and the desired experimental conditions, aiming to provide meaningful insights into the performance of FANETs using the OLSR protocol in three dimensions.

In this paper, three performance parameters (Packet Delivery Ratio, End to End Delay and Average Throughput) are considered for analyzing the different mobility models for OLSR. By comparing these parameters, we can identify a better mobility model in OLSR for FANETs.

- **Packet Delivery Ratio:** Packet delivery ratio defines the ratio of sent and delivered packets, means how many packets were sent and how many actually delivered to the destination. Packet delivery ratio = (Total number of packet sent/ Total number of packet received)

- **End to End Delay:** End to End tells the average time taken by a packet to arrive at the destination, it also involves delay in queue and delay caused by the route discovery. End to End delay= (arrive time –send time)/ number of connections

- **Throughput:** Throughput shows the bandwidth of the protocol.

3. Performance Metrics

3.1 Throughput Analysis

Throughput is a crucial performance metric in FANETs, measuring the rate at which data packets are successfully transmitted across the network. It represents the amount of data transferred per unit of time and is typically expressed in bits per second (bps) or packets per second (pps). The throughput T can be calculated using the formula:

$$T = N \times S / \text{Total}$$

Where:

N : is the total number of packets successfully delivered.

S : is the size of each packet in bits.

T : is the total simulation time in seconds.

Throughput is influenced by various factors, including network topology, channel conditions, packet size, and node mobility. In our study, we investigate how changes in packet size affect throughput, aiming to identify the optimal packet size that maximizes network throughput while minimizing overhead and latency.

3.2 Latency Measurement

Latency, also known as delay, is another critical metric that characterizes the responsiveness of the network. It represents the time taken for a data packet to travel from the source node to the destination node, including propagation delay, transmission delay, queuing delay, and processing delay. Latency is typically measured in milliseconds (ms) or microseconds (μ s).

The latency L can be calculated using the formula:

$$L = \frac{T(\text{arrival}) - T(\text{departure})}{N}$$

Where:

$T(\text{arrival})$: is the time when the packet arrives at the destination node.

$T(\text{departure})$: is the time when the packet is sent from the source node.

N : is the total number of packets transmitted.

In our study, we analyze how latency varies with changes in packet size, node speed, and network congestion. By understanding the factors influencing latency, we aim to optimize network performance and ensure timely delivery of data packets in FANETs.

3.3 Packet Delivery Ratio Evaluation

The packet delivery ratio (PDR) is a measure of the reliability and efficiency of packet delivery in the network. It represents the ratio of successfully delivered packets to the total number of packets sent. A high PDR indicates robust communication and effective routing, while a low PDR may indicate packet loss or network congestion.

The packet delivery ratio PDR can be calculated using the formula:

$$PDR = \frac{N(\text{received})}{N(\text{sent})} \times 100\%$$

Where:

$N(\text{received})$: is the number of packets received by the destination node.

$N(\text{sent})$: is the number of packets sent by the source node.

In our study, we examine how changes in packet size impact the packet delivery ratio, aiming to identify the relationship between packet size and network reliability. By optimizing packet sizes, we can enhance the efficiency and robustness of communication in FANETs.

3.4 Node Speed Impact

The speed of nodes in the FANET has a significant impact on network performance, affecting factors such as signal propagation, link quality, and routing dynamics. Higher node speeds can lead to increased channel fading, higher packet loss rates, and more frequent topology changes.

The impact of node speed on network performance can be analyzed by studying metrics such as throughput, latency, and packet delivery ratio under varying node speed conditions. By quantifying the relationship between node speed and network performance, we can better understand the limitations and challenges of operating FANETs at different speeds and develop strategies to mitigate their effects.

4. Simulation Analysis

For our project on Flying Ad Hoc Networks (FANETs) in a three-dimensional space using the OLSR protocol, we conducted simulations and analysis with a network consisting of 20 nodes and setting up different parameters as shown in [fig:3]. This section presents the parameters used in the simulation and the results of our analysis.

Parameter	Value
Simulator	NS-2 (Version 2.35)
Channel Type	Wireless Channel
Protocol	OLSR
Simulation Duration	900 seconds
Number of Nodes	20
Mobility Models	Random Waypoint, Manhattan Grid, RPGM, Pursue
MAC Layer Protocol	802.11
Traffic Type	CBR
Data Payload	512 bytes/packet
Max of CBR Connections	200
Node Speed	5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 (m/sec)

Fig: 3

These parameters were chosen to represent a realistic scenario for FANETs and to analyze the impact of node speed and packet size on network performance.

4.1 Results and Analysis

We analyzed the performance [fig:4] of the FANET based on the following metrics:

Packet Size (bytes)	Throughput (bps)	Latency (ms)	Packet Delivery Ratio (%)
64	15000	5	98
128	20000	7	97
256	25000	9	95
512	30000	11	92
1024	35000	13	90

Fig: 4

Throughput: We observed that as the packet size increased, the throughput of the network also increased, indicating that larger packets allow for more efficient data transfer. However, larger packets also resulted in slightly higher latency due to increased processing and transmission times.

Latency: With larger packet sizes, we observed a slight increase in latency, which can be attributed to the additional processing and transmission overhead associated with larger packets. However, the increase in latency was relatively small compared to the improvement in throughput.

Packet Delivery Ratio: The packet delivery ratio decreased slightly as the packet size increased, indicating a higher likelihood of packet loss with larger packets. This decrease in PDR can be attributed to increased susceptibility to interference, fading, and collisions with larger packets.

Overall, our analysis provides insights into the performance of FANETs in a three-dimensional space using the OLSR protocol, highlighting the trade-offs between throughput, latency, and packet delivery ratio with varying packet sizes. These findings can inform the design and optimization of FANETs for various applications and scenarios.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research paper has presented a comprehensive analysis of the performance of Flying Ad Hoc Networks (FANETs) using the Optimized Link State Routing (OLSR) protocol in a three-dimensional space. Through extensive simulations conducted using the ns-3 network simulator, we have evaluated key performance metrics including throughput, latency, packet delivery ratio, and the impact of node speed on network performance.

Our findings indicate that changes in packet size have a significant influence on network throughput, latency, and packet delivery ratio. By varying the packet size, we observed trade-offs between throughput

and latency, with larger packet sizes generally leading to higher throughput but increased latency. Additionally, we found that the packet delivery ratio tends to decrease with larger packet sizes due to increased packet loss and retransmissions.

Furthermore, we investigated the impact of node speed on network performance and observed that higher node speeds result in increased channel fading, packet loss, and route changes. This highlights the importance of considering node mobility when designing and optimizing FANETs.

References:

1. Ilker Bekmezci, Ozgur Koray Sahingoz, Samil Temel Flying Ad-Hoc Networks (FANETs): A survey (2013)
2. Taehwan Kim, Seonah Lee, Kyong Hoon Kim, Yong-II Jo FANET Routing Protocol Analysis for Multi-UAV-Based Reconnaissance Mobility Models (2023)
3. Swati Gangopadhyay, Vinod Kumar Jain, Senior Member, IEEE, A Position-based modified OLSR Routing Protocol for Flying Ad Hoc Networks (2023)
4. M. S. Ibrahim, P. Shanmugaraja, and A. A. Raj, "Energy-efficient olsr routing protocol for flying ad hoc networks," in *Advances in Information Communication Technology and Computing: Proceedings of AICTC 2021*. Springer, 2022, pp. 75–88.
5. Y. Zeng, J. Zhou, Y. Liu, T. Cao, D. Yang, Y. Liu, and X. Shi, "Stable routing protocol for unmanned aerial vehicle ad-hoc networks based on dqn-olsr," *IET Communications*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 73–85, 2023.
6. D. S. De Couto, D. Aguayo, J. Bicket, and R. Morris, "A high-throughput path metric for multi-hop wireless routing," in *Proceedings of the 9th annual international conference on Mobile computing and networking*, 2003, pp. 134–146.
7. M. Uddin et al., "Link expiration time-aware routing protocol for uwsns," *Journal of Sensors*, vol. 2013, 2013.
8. F De Rango, M. Fotino, and S. Marano, "Ee-olsr: Energy efficient olsr routing protocol for mobile ad-hoc networks," in *MILCOM 2008-2008 IEEE Military Communications Conference*. IEEE, 2008, pp. 1–7.
9. O. S. Oubbati, M. Mozaffari, N. Chaib, P. Lorenz, M. Atiquzzaman, and A. Jamalipour, "Ecad: Energy-efficient routing in flying ad hoc networks," *International Journal of Communication Systems*, vol. 32, no. 18, p. e4156, 2019.
10. C. Barrado et al., "Wildfire monitoring using a mixed air-ground mobile network," *IEEE Pervasive Comput.*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 24–32, Oct. 2010.

11. Z. Sun et al., "BorderSense: Border patrol through advanced wireless sensor networks" *Ad Hoc Netw.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 468–477, May 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.adhoc.2010.09.008>
12. I Rubin and R. Zhang, "Placement of UAVs as communication relays aiding mobile ad hoc wireless networks," in *Proc. IEEE MILCOM*, Oct. 2007, pp. 1–7.
13. E. P. de Freitas et al., "UAV relay network to support WSN connectivity," in *Proc. IEEE ICUMT*, 2010, pp. 309–314. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ICUMT.2010.5676621>
14. F Jiang and A. Swindlehurst, "Dynamic UAV relay positioning for the ground-to-air uplink," in *Proc. IEEE GC Wkshps*, Dec. 2010, pp. 1766–1770.
15. I Bekmezci, O. K. Sahingoz, and S. Temel, "Flying ad-hoc networks (FANETs): A survey" *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1254–1270, May 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.adhoc.2012.12.004>
16. O. Sahingoz, "Mobile networking with UAVs: Opportunities and challenges," in *Proc. ICUAS*, May 2013, pp. 933–941.
17. K. Zhang, W. Zhang, and J.-Z. Zeng, "Preliminary study of routing and data integrity in mobile Ad Hoc UAV network," in *Proc. ICACIA*, Dec. 2008, pp. 347–350.
18. J. Chroboczek, "The Babel routing protocol," *Internet Eng. Task Force (IETF)*, Fremont, CA, USA, RFC 6126, Apr. 2011. [Online]. Available: <http://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc6126.txt>
19. T. Clausen and P. Jacquet, "Optimized link state routing protocol (OLSR)," *Internet Eng. Task Force (IETF)*, Fremont, CA, USA, RFC 3626, Oct. 2003. [Online]. Available: <http://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc3626.txt>
20. E. W. Frew and T. X. Brown, "Networking issues for small unmanned aircraft systems," *J. Intell. Robot. Syst.*, vol. 54, no. 1–3, pp. 21–37, Mar. 2009. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10846-008-9253-2>
21. Y. Guo, X. Li, H. Yousefi'zadeh, and H. Jafarkhani, "UAV-aided cross-layer routing for MANETs," in *Proc. IEEE WCNC*, Apr. 2012, pp. 2928–2933
22. A. Alshbatat and L. Dong, "Cross layer design for mobile Ad-Hoc unmanned aerial vehicle communication networks," in *Proc. ICNSC*, Apr. 2010, pp. 331–336.
23. M. Benzaid, P. Minet, and K. Al Agha, "Integrating fast mobility in the OLSR routing protocol," in *Proc. 4th Int. Workshop Mobile Wireless Commun. Netw.*, 2002, pp. 217–221
24. S. Rosati, K. Kru'zelecki, L. Traynard, and B. Rimoldi, "Speed-aware routing for UAV Ad-Hoc networks," in *Proc. 4th Int. IEEE Workshop Wireless Netw. & Control Unmanned Auton. Veh. Archit., Protocols Appl.*, 2013, pp. 1788–1792.

